

Knowledge-guided segmentation of iso-intense infant brain

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Abstract. Tissue segmentation of infants could lead to early diagnosis of neurological disorders, potentially enabling early interventions. However, the challenge of tissue quantification is increased due to the very dynamic changes that happen as brain development advances over the course of the first year. One of the structural processes is the myelination which causes limited contrast between gray and white matter tissue on T1-weighted and T2-weighted magnetic resonance images at around six to nine months. In recent years, as a result of the MICCAI brain MRI segmentation challenge in 6-month old infants (iSeg17 and iSeg19), there has been an increase in interest in this complex task. In this work, we propose two methodologies to overcome issues of erroneous segmentation on the border between gray and white matter, based on knowledge-guided U-Net for segmenting the iso-intense infant brain. First, segmentation was guided using a prior of white matter obtained from an atlas for developing infants. Second, segmentation was focused on the low-intensity contrast boundary between white and gray matter. Experimental results on the subjects of iSeg19 challenge display the potential of utilizing the white matter prior as input for segmentation. Overall, its utilization leads to results that are closer to the brain anatomy with smoother and connected white matter regions.

Keywords: Guided segmentation · Iso-intense phase · Brain quantification.

1 Introduction

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) allows the study of the brain in-vivo. Neurological disorders could potentially be identified before their onset by detecting brain anomalies [8]. Specifically, MRI quantification of the brain tissues (i.e., white matter (WM) and gray matter (GM)) has been proven to be helpful for

the early detection of neurological disorders such as schizophrenia [6] and autism [7].

Despite the potential clinical value of developing automatic methods in infants, MRI quantification of very young patients (i.e., from birth to 2 years old) presents multiple challenges. Infant MR scans suffer from lower quality as a result of increased partial volume effect due to smaller brain size, and motion artifacts [25]. In addition, rapid and non-linear neurodevelopmental changes contribute to heterogeneous intensities in MR images leading to unclear borders between GM and WM and regional variations in contrast [16]. Furthermore, equipment manufacturers, magnetic field strength, and acquisition protocol can affect the contrast and intensity distribution in acquired images leading to multi-site heterogeneity issues [19].

The isointense phase occurs at around 6 to 9 months of age and is defined as the period when GM and WM intensities overlap (see Fig.1). The myelination, which progresses from central to peripheral brain regions, causes GM and WM to exhibit similar intensities (in both T1-weighted and T2-weighted images). As a result of limited contrast between GM and WM, tissue quantification is extremely challenging.

Fig. 1: Brain MRI in the isointense phase of brain development. The first row displays T1-weighted images and the second-row T2-weighted images in axial, coronal, sagittal view and corresponding tissue intensity distributions, respectively.

Previous research in the isointense brain segmentation can be split into three categories: atlas-based methods, learning-based methods, and hybrid approaches. Employing atlas-based methods depends highly on the present contrast in the MR images and can be time-consuming [25]. Learning based-methods are further split into machine learning [21, 22] and deep learning methods [2, 5, 10], with some deep learning methods employing the longitudinal data to guide the segmentation [3]. Generally, deep learning methods enable automatic learning of more representative and discriminative features, whereas classical machine

learning methods require explicit data characterization through hand-crafted features [4, 11, 13]. Alternatively, hybrid approaches [18] integrate multiple strategies into a final pipeline.

Deep learning-based networks have a consistently good performance. However, they suffer from persistent errors present at the border between GM and WM. Recent works demonstrate the potential of utilizing prior anatomical knowledge to guide the segmentation. For example, Kushibar et al [9] utilize spatial features extracted from a structural probabilistic atlas to guide the segmentation in sub-cortical brain structure. Furthermore, Wang et al [22, 23] introduce a signed distance map in a two-stage sequential segmentation process. The signed distance maps assure the presence of WM inside GM and guide the final segmentation result.

Inspired by these approaches and considering there are numerous ways of introducing prior information, two new methodologies are proposed for dealing with the isointense stage of brain development. The first adds prior information regarding WM localization obtained from an atlas, in combination with T1-weighted and T2-weighted images as input to a neural network. This approach uses previously defined tissue labels on reference MR images (i.e. atlas) as prior knowledge to segment a target image. In the second method, inspired by the works of Navarro et al. in multi-organ segmentation [14], we define modeling the boundary between gray and white matter to guide the segmentation in unclear regions.

2 Methodology

2.1 Dataset and Atlas

iSeg19 is a publicly available dataset provided by MICCAI challenge [19]. This dataset consists of T1-weighted and T2-weighted images of infants aged 6 ± 0.8 months. The fully pre-processed dataset (resampled, skull-stripped, with corrected inhomogeneities and cerebellum and brain stem removed) consists of ten training samples containing both intensity and ground truth (GT) images and thirteen cases of only intensity images for validation. Experiments were performed on the training dataset and the best-performing pipeline was further tested on the validation dataset.

Annotation of CSF, WM, and GM of the dataset was done by the iSeg19 challenge organizers.

Atlas for developing infants provided by Zhang et al. (2016) [24] gives information on common brain anatomy of 6 months old infants in standardized space.

2.2 Data Preparation

Pre-processing the data reduces the variability across subjects. Firstly, in each image, the intensities above the 99 percentile and below 1 percentile were

cropped, removing the influence of outliers. Secondly, a min-max normalization was used to scale the values between 0 and 1. Finally, a data augmentation technique of flipping was implemented to increase the number of volumes during training. The dataset was doubled by including left-to-right flipped volumes in training, taking into account the pseudo-symmetrical nature of the left and right hemispheres of the brain.

Fig. 2: Pipeline for extracting prior information from the atlas

Anatomical Prior was derived utilizing image registration to align the atlas and the particular subject. Specifically, the T1-weighted image of the subject and the T1-weighted atlas were registered. A sequential process of implementing affine [15] and non-rigid [12] registrations was used to provide the deformation map for label propagation of the atlas segmentation to the subject space. The propagation of the labels was followed by extracting only the WM segmentation and processing it using erosion and Gaussian blurring. The initial usage of erosion was done given the imperfect alignment between the ground truth and the propagated labels. The Gaussian blurring was implemented to smooth the anatomical prior. The blurring level was manually adjusted trying to preserve reasonable information, sigma was set to 3.

Patch Extraction technique was employed as a result of limited number of samples available for training. The overlap was introduced by decreasing the patch stride to be smaller than the patch size, with the patch size being 16x16x16 and patch stride 8x8x8. Only patches that include at least a predefined portion of genuine brain volume were considered in training.

2.3 Deep Learning Network

U-Net is a well-known state-of-the-art deep learning network for biomedical image segmentation [17]. This network has been extensively used to segment the isointense phase of brain development [19, 23].

Training parameters utilized for both networks explained in the next two subsections include Adam optimizer, batch size of 32 and 100 epochs with early stopping. Furthermore, dropout is introduced to prevent overfitting.

The following two networks were developed and tested:

Fig. 3: Illustrations of U-Net architectures developed

I. White Matter Prior In this case the U-Net network (Fig. 3a) is trained using three inputs, T1-weighted, T2-weighted and WM prior information acquired from an atlas. The loss function is categorical cross-entropy.

II. Multi-branch U-Net We develop a complementary learning task where second to last decoder block splits into two separate decoder blocks each with its own softmax activation function. The segmentation is output by one, while the contour representing the boundary between gray and white matter is output by the other. As there are two separate outputs, the optimized loss function is the sum of objectives of the related tasks, i.e., segmentation (categorical cross-entropy) and contour prediction (binary cross-entropy).

$$L_{total} = L_{tissue} + L_{contour}$$

$$L_{tissue} = - \sum_{c=1}^M \sum_{o=1}^N y_{o,c} \log(p_{o,c})$$

$$L_{contour} = - \sum_{c=1}^M (y_c \log(p) + (1 - y_c) \log(1 - p))$$

where M - number of classes, N - number of observations, y - binary indicator (0 or 1) if class label c is the correct classification for observation o , and p - predicted probability that observation o is of class c .

2.4 Implementation Details

This project was implemented using Python programming language. Complementary libraries used include numpy, nibabel, patchify and matplotlib. Image registration was done using icometrix’s implementation of NiftyReg [12, 15]. Erosion and blurring of the registered atlas were done using scikit-image package [20]. The 3D U-Net was implemented using Tensorflow [1].

3 Experiments and results

A leave-one-out cross-validation was employed during training to obtain the optimal parameters and evaluate the effects of introducing prior information. Nine subjects would be used for training and one subject for testing. During the network training, the training subjects would be further split using an 80%/20% strategy. The metric used for evaluation of training results is Dice similarity coefficient (DSC). For the validation dataset of the challenge, as provided by the challenge’s organizers once the segmentation results have been submitted, the metrics also include 95th percentile Hausdorff distance (HD) and average surface distance (ASD).

Once labels of the atlas have been propagated to the patient space using distinct deformation maps, five experiments were performed as follows: i) baseline U-Net (using no prior information); ii) using WM prior; iii) using GM prior on WM prior trained network to observe if the network is utilizing the WM information for prediction; iv) using *perfect* prior which is obtained from the ground truth to observe the potential result in case of *perfect* image registration and v) adding contour to guide the segmentation.

Quantitative Results Figure 4 illustrates effects of adding prior information. Employing the WM prior as an extra input channel leads to a slight increase in the WM and GM DSC value when compared to the baseline U-Net. The utilization of the prior by the network is further confirmed when using the GM prior for prediction on a WM prior trained network. In this case, we attribute the small decrease in DSC for CSF to the prior not affecting that location, and a considerable decrease of 16.1% for GM and 25.1% for WM to the effect of using misleading information as input. The potential of utilizing this type of information is further tested when utilizing the *perfect* prior obtained from the GT and processed in the same manner as previously explained. In this case, an increase of 0.9% in the case of CSF, 4.5% in the case of GM, and 7.2% in the case of WM when compared to the results of the model “With Prior” information is observed. In contrast, complementary task learning (i.e., adding the WM/GM contour as second output) did not improve the results.

Fig. 4: Value of DSC for different tissue classes for each one of the experiments on the training dataset showcased on x-axis.

Qualitative Results Figure 5 shows a qualitative comparison between using the baseline network and the networks guided by the prior. The WM prior obtained with label propagation leads to more anatomically accurate results similar to those present in GT with smooth and connected WM regions as we can observe from the highlighted regions.

Fig. 5: Qualitative improvement in segmentation when using the WM prior. The 1st column shows the GT, 2nd column showcases the segmentation results of the baseline U-Net with no prior information, 3rd column when using the WM prior obtained with the label propagation, and 4th column displays the multi-branch U-Net.

3.1 iSeg19 Validation Dataset

The final model including anatomical guidance using WM prior was tested on the validation dataset of the iSeg19 challenge. This model was trained on the complete training dataset with the number of epochs set to 42 as that was the average number of epochs needed for convergence in the leave-one-out strategy.

As a result of adequate training (avoiding over-fitting), a good generalization performance is observed, since the segmentation results are coherent with those obtained during training (see Table 1. Furthermore, Hausdorff distance (HD) for WM falls in the top 4 of the challenge results on the validation dataset as consulted from the iSeg19 website (on the date 11/07/2022).

	CSF	GM	WM
DSC	0.927 (0.007)	0.891 (0.009)	0.860 (0.016)
HD	10.023 (1.659)	7.340 (1.247)	6.659 (1.020)
ASD	0.197 (0.017)	0.437 (0.038)	0.499 (0.048)

Table 1: Average mean and standard deviation DSC, HD, and ASD on the validation dataset of the iSeg19 challenge, provided by the organizers once the segmentation results have been submitted.

4 Discussion and conclusions

In this work, we propose a solution for introducing prior information to the challenging task of segmenting infant tissue in the isointense phase, characterized by the limited distinction between GM and WM tissue on T1-weighted and T2-weighted images.

Overall, experimental results on the iSeg19 dataset showcase a slight increase in performance when utilizing the WM tissue prior. Visual analysis of the above results demonstrates more refined segmentation in sub-cortical regions when using information of the WM localization.

The multi-branch U-Net did not perform better than the proposed alternative. This could be due to the fact that the choice of the loss function and of the weighting between the two losses was not fully optimized.

With the exception of the Hausdorff distance metric, the results obtained on the iSeg19 validation dataset were not as good as the top performing challenge participants. This might be explained by the fact that we used an easy-to-train and well-established U-net network that is presumably less optimized compared to more complex architectures.

The presented work is limited to the data only related to the 6-month old infants, although the isointense phase occurs at around 6 to 9 months. Furthermore, the developed method requires both T1 and T2-weighted images. Future work includes further improving the registration between the atlas and the specific subject as well as optimizing the network, considering a simple U-Net architecture was implemented to test the effect of this type of prior.

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